

Marketing the Hotel Sector in the Holy City of Najaf: An Analytical Study of the Design, Spaces, and Areas of Hotel Rooms

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Abstract

The hotel sector is one of the most essential tourism sectors in developing or developed countries, as it contributes significantly to economic growth. Design by nature belongs to the plastic arts, and the art of creation is a comprehensive field that includes many specializations. Any design process needs a clear plan as well. Each type of design aims to achieve a specific function, and the study of architectural spaces, including the elements, foundations, and determinants they contain, is considered one of the most critical architectural studies, especially modern ones. It is a study that simulates man in an attempt to form an understandable language between man and the surroundings or the space he inhabits. The architectural space, with its physical composition, functional form, and aesthetic appearance, is the vessel in which humanity interacts to form civilization, which is considered the highest and finest creation of society, as the holy city of Najaf possesses distinct tourism components that make it It deserves to receive millions of tourists from all over the world, as it includes traces of multiple and ancient civilizations, enjoys a Mediterranean climate and provides essential infrastructure such as road and communications networks and trained tourism and hotel human resources, which constitutes a necessary base for the tourism industry and natural tourism recovery. Tourist hotels are one of the fundamental pillars on which tourism and hotel programs depend. The hospitality industry is considered the country's cultural interface and the window through which tourists view the services and facilities provided for the stay and comfort of guests. They also represent a direct, practical translation of local culture regarding architectural style, construction style, interior design, and equipment—hotel, hospitality, communications, and transportation. From experience and comparison, foreign tourists notice that Najaf Al-Ashraf has the vast majority of tourist hotel services and buildings in Iraq that are not at the required level. In this research, we confirm that tourist hotel buildings equipped and designed on scientific foundations majorly in marketing the Iraqi tourism and hotel industry. From this standpoint, we focus on the primary service function in the hotel, which is the hotel room, in terms of studying and analyzing the interior design of the room (such as the spatial dimensions of the room, internal distribution and functional connectivity, color study, lighting, orientation and movement...etc.) and focuses on studying all elements of interior design (Finishes, materials, colors used, furnishings, lighting elements, and technical services). The study confirms the relationship of the previous aspects of the interior design of the residence room to the environment (cultural, social, and surrounding climate).

Keywords: marketing, hotels, design

Chapter One

The Theoretical Framework of the Research

First: The Research Problem

What is the study of design, spaces, and areas of hotel rooms in the hotel sector in the holy city of Najaf? Is there interest of designers and hotel owners in hotels' interior and exterior design in Najaf Governorate?

Second: Research hypotheses

It is known that a hypothesis is a guess based on experience and accurate observation of relationships and their causes. The idea does not come out of nowhere; instead, it is a possible answer to the research question or a result of an expected action. It can be formulated in two ways: conditional and declarative. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study came in a declarative form that says:

(Religious tourism in the Holy City of Najaf could not outperform religious tourism in Holy Karbala because it needed help finding a clearly defined philosophy that explains this and because it faced many challenges and neglected many opportunities.) The process of creating excellence within hotels is linked to technological adaptation.

Third: Research Objectives

- 1- Recognizing the importance of industry excellence for tourist hotels.
- 2- Learn about the study of design, spaces, and areas of hotel rooms.
- 3- Knowing the importance of the hotel's bioclimatic architecture design goals.
- 4 - Knowing the hotel's impact on the number of employees and capacity.

Fourth: The Importance Of Research

The importance of the hotel industry in the city of Najaf, the tourism and hotel services it carries within it, and the resources it can achieve as an alternative to the oil on which our dear country, Iraq, depends almost entirely in running its economic affairs, and what this tourism can bring to the city of Najaf. Of luxury and development, as this is one of the few academic contributions in an unusual form, by addressing its philosophy, the nature of the challenges it faces, and the opportunities available to it, and analyzing the indicators of the hotel sector in this city, during the last seven years, it has tried to direct attention towards the hotel industry in the town as it is a virgin market that is still cut off. A set of conclusions and recommendations can be reached about the changes in the modern global hospitality industry that help determine future paths and treatments for the hotel sector.

Fifth: Limits of research

Spatial boundaries: Hotel accommodation rooms in Najaf of the tourist category (three, four, and five stars). Their locations will be indicated in the hotels referred to in the field research.

Temporal limits: The time limits of the research are the period during which the research models were created up to the present day. The study focuses on the accommodation rooms of hotels in the city of Najaf in the tourist category (three, four, and five stars) because this category is one of the most frequented by Arab and foreign tourists (according to statistics from the Tourism Authority). Then, determine the extent to which these models interact with the data of the surrounding cultural environment and achieve the concept of sustainability while comparing them with Arab and international experiences. The analytical study includes the following:

1- The architectural and interior design of the rooms (the suitability of the spatial dimensions of the rooms and the quality of the functional distribution).

2- Furnishings and interior furnishing of rooms (quality, shape, style, identity, surface covering, quality of materials and colors used, and their functional and environmental performance).

3- Technical, service, and health equipment (quality and effectiveness of heating, air conditioning, lighting, telephone, television, and health services used).

Sixth: Research structure

The structure of our research includes four sections. We addressed in the first section: {the research problem, the research hypothesis, the research objectives, the research methodology, and the research structure}. The second section included the concept and types of the hotel excellence industry (hotel marketing for tourist hotels). The third section deals with the strategy of the sector of tourism excellence in hotels in Najaf Al-Ashraf in terms of the number of hotels, capacity, number of workers in the industry, and a description of the production factors contributing to the hotel sector. The fourth section is the conclusions, recommendations, and sources.

Chapter Two: Industry Excellence (Hotel Marketing for Tourist Hotels)

First: Hotels in the hospitality industry: concept and types

The hospitality industry is one of the modern and advanced economic service sectors, and its success represents success and economic recovery for countries that depend on this advanced industry. It seeks to achieve satisfaction and contentment among the guests by providing multiple and varied services. The services provided to the tourist from his arrival to the country until his return to his country of origin include comfortable and safe accommodation, food and beverage services, and entertainment.

1- Definition of hotel

Some researchers have tended to define the hotel institution as an organization that seeks to achieve social goals. They described it as an organized social arrangement created intentionally to achieve common collective goals through an excellent structural structure and administrative practices. In other words, it is “an administrative organization with economic and social characteristics that provides hospitality within the framework of local and international laws, in exchange for a specific fee for a guest inside a building designed for this purpose.

The American Association defined a hotel as “an inn prepared by the provisions of the law so that the guest can find shelter, food, and other services in return for a known fee.” British law defines the hotel as: “a place where the obligor receives shelter and food services for a specific price that he can pay.” Accordingly, the previous definitions define the hotel as: “a place where the resident/tourist/guest, guest, or client is referred to all the services that he can obtain.” but for a pre-agreed fee.

2- Types of hotels

Hotels and their types vary depending on ownership, location, services, and other considerations indicated by researchers. We can classify hotel types according to the following:

A - Ownership: It is divided into several sections as follows: ⁴

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1. Mohamed Hafez Hegazy, Hotel Organizations Management, 2011, Alexandria, p. 10.
 2. Ali Zayan Zerrougui, Intellectual Capital as a Competitive Advantage for the Hotel Founder, Algeria 2011, p. 10.

3. Issam Hussein Al-Saidi, Hotel Organizations Management, 2008, p. 31.
4. Hala Hussein Al-Sayyid, Principles of the Hospitality Industry, Alexandria, 2008, p. 95.

- Private sector hotels: These are owned by one or more people or a family who pay for construction, furnishing, equipping, and operating operations.
- Chain hotels: A chain hotel is a group of hotels spread across a group of countries worldwide that operate under one name and are operated and managed by the directives of the central management of the hotel chain (the parent company). The central management charges from these hotels prescribed fees or percentages of profits in exchange for using the trade name and trademark of the hotel chain.
- Mixed sector hotels: Their ownership is shared between the government and the private sector or any foreign company specializing in hotels.
- Entirely government hotels: They are private property of the state and may be subject to state ownership or ownership by one of the state agencies.

B- Services: They are divided into the following: 1.

- Commercial hotels: To serve those who frequent significant commercial or industrial traffic, these hotels adopt modern technology to provide high-end services.
- Therapeutic hotels: They are located near therapeutic places. They may be healthy water wells or a sand area with medicinal properties. This type of hotel requires that it be found in a fit size and in the middle of green spaces, considering that the hotel's furnishing is appropriate to the guests' medical conditions.

Second: Hotel design standards

Hotel design standards vary, and they address many international settings and measures to ensure the space's effectiveness and the user's well-being. Among them, we find standards for site design, orientation, car access, entry lobby, public halls, cafeteria hall, bedrooms...etc. The following table shows these standards:

1- Location: The location changes according to the nature and importance of the hotel, as it is chosen close to stations, call centers, and areas of commercial or recreational importance, as well as in quiet commercial or critical neighborhoods not exposed to dust and wooded areas, in addition to spacious yards and private parking areas. The site is as far away from schools and clinics as possible.

2- Orientation: Guest rooms are oriented towards the east, west, or south. The kitchen, service halls, and employee rooms face north

3- Entry of cars: It is preferable to ensure the movement of vehicles up to the main covered entrance and give sufficient width for entry and exit movement (lobby + movement - parking + waiting).

4- Entry lobby: The entry lobby forms the hotel's heart and must allow access to the entire hotel. It must also contain stairs, elevators, and an information corner. In many cases, the lobby forms a covered garden around which various halls designated for guests gather, such as cafeteria halls for guests, and it must be for the restaurant. Private entrance. The dining hall, which can accommodate half of the hotel's capacity

5- Public hall: Public halls are often gathered on one floor and separated from each other by light partitions that allow them to be opened over each other. They form a large hall for celebrations

when needed. In this case, providing a private entrance with changing places and bathrooms is necessary.

6- Cafeteria hall: It is usually on the ground floor, and in some large cities, hotels only contain some simple galleries for breakfast and rest.

7- Bedrooms: The bedrooms start from the first floor, and the rooms overlook courtyards or gardens and face towards the east or south, while the shallow rooms overlook an internal garden. The height of the rooms is 2.8 m or less. In the large shared halls, each person is allocated a space of no less than 3 m². In private rooms, each person is given an area of 8.6 m², and the air volume is no less than 12 m³.

Room Furniture:

T - Beds: Several sizes vary in width, but the length is fixed. The American bed is 206 cm long. This measurement is adopted in most international hotels. Bed design: The head of the bed is essential for reading, hairdressing, protecting wall coverings, and providing thermal insulation. The head of the bed is an integral part of the room's equipment. The bed has mattresses and protective covers or pillowcases that can be moved during cleaning procedures. Moving the beds quickly is extremely important to facilitate the cleaning process underneath.

- A bed with a width of (103 cm) for one person.
- Bed (single and a half) with full width (133 cm) for one person wide
- A double bed (queen, 147 cm) designated for a couple.
- Double bed (queen width 177 cm), limited to motels and designated for couples.
- A double bed with a width of (191 cm) for a couple.
- The foldable bed as a sofa: It can be distributed in the room instead of one of the beds, providing a comfortable space for sitting during the day. When necessary, the sofa can be folded to turn into a bed.

D - Cabinet: arranged in a distributor with drawers. Such furniture requires a minimum of (44 cm) and is often preferred (59 cm) for opening drawers and hanging clothes.

C - Luggage rack or stand: A fixed piece of furniture arranged in the distributor. Since the guest usually leaves his luggage in the room, placing a good amount of furniture instead of a foldable luggage rack is preferable.

1. Mona Tawfiq, Relationship Marketing (Research and Studies), Egypt, 2005, p. 25.
2. Mahmoud Abdel Muti Al-Buhaisi, The Role of Empowering Employees in Achieving Institutional Excellence, A Field Study on Technical Colleges in the Governorates of the Gaza Strip, Palestine, 2014, p. 84.

H - Tables: such as a cocktail table, as this allows for a low table to be used for eating, playing cards, or writing. There are many tables called cocktail tables, which are relatively upright lamps that combine two pieces of furniture into one: the cocktail table and the excellent lamp. Such exploitation of space is more space-saving, as the light is in the desired place, and there is no need for a moving lamp.

G- The writing and dressing table: The table became a standard for combining a cabinet containing drawers with furniture.

D - Chairs: The room has two types of chairs; the first has a straight backrest or an upholstered seat in front of the writing and dressing table. The second type is one or two armchairs for sitting and resting, with a cocktail table between them.

D - Cocktail table: It is used to place drinks, books, or luggage or to serve meals, or it can be used as a cart if cupboards are added to it. The designer must consider that if the dining table is not movable, there must be enough space inside the room to place the portable room service table on wheels.

T - Lighting design: Lighting depends on the skill of the interior designer. The necessary lighting lamps may be equipped with additional lighting to create a cheerful and comfortable environment. Control of these lamps must be given great importance. The simplest type of control involves a switch on the door that turns on one, two, or even all of the lamps in the room. Types of lighting and their possibilities:

- Ceiling lighting: Lamps or fixtures must be considered in the ceiling above the seating area.
- Double lamp: It must be hot (yellow lighting) and placed on the evening table between the two beds. This type of lighting provides direct and sufficient light for one guest to read on the bed while the other can sleep without disturbance from his partner's lighting.
- Lighting at the head of the bed: It is installed either at the head of the upholstered wooden bed or on the wall next to it. This means there are two lighting outlets for a pair of lamps for the double bed, each of which can be used independently.

G - Special lighting for writing or decoration: This usually requires a table on which the guest may sit and write, or the woman may sit to perform the decorating tasks.

Q - The view: Looking out the window is a good experience for any living room guest.

Third: Modern global trends in hotel room design

Modern hotel design is responsible for the most daring, colorful, and imaginative creations than any other architectural category, and there has been a great diversity of hotel designs and styles. Today, the scenes feature diverse influences that allow business travelers and individuals on vacation to enjoy many options. Taste is also significant, and spending is substantial, as price and economy class are considered. Culture and awareness among educated hotel patrons play an essential role in choosing hotel service.

The hotel room design style in its traditional form (within the primary trend of the hospitality industry) that adopts separate pieces of furniture (as explained under the title Room Furniture) has continued for an extended period since the beginning of the twentieth century without deviating much from the norm in most countries of the world. However, many attempts to redesign the room consistent with the development of design methods and their various trends began to appear at the end of the twentieth century. The first of these attempts began by integrating some functions in the room with each other. Modern trends in hotel room design appear today in both European and American countries. Very diverse movements, most of which participate freely in treating the interior furnishings and creating entirely new and innovative interconnections, such as making the wall separating the bathroom room. For example, a bedroom made of glass (it is not socially acceptable in our country) or recreating unfamiliar relationships between the elements of the room's interior space and its functions. On the other hand, we find a trend in most countries with a long cultural heritage, such as Japan, China, India, and the Arab countries, to recreate traditional interior environments. They are reviving it and presenting it in a contemporary way, combining tradition with Western ideas of comfort.

Fourth: Functional distribution, orientation, and movement of rooms

The field research showed that the hotels in the city of Najaf, the research subject, are invested at very high rates in most tourist seasons despite the deteriorating internal environments that the research will show. The fact that tourists use the room shows the need to design the functions of the dispenser, the bathroom, and the room with extreme precision. One of the criteria for the good interior design of a residence room is measured by the designer's ability to utilize the available space¹ and distribute it among the three main parts (the distributor, the bathroom, and the room) effectively and practically while ensuring easy movement and the ability to maintain the sanitary unit periodically. One of the essential tasks of field research is to raise the dimensions of the space. Accurately measure the interior and interior furnishings, then redraw the architectural plans for the research models and test the quality of the interior design, if any². Unfortunately, this was not available in most of the models studied, as the use of spaces between the three functions that make up the room in some research models created many problems (we will monitor them in the research). It was most likely not based on a precise scientific design study, and the table shows the disparity in the proportions. Divide the total area of each room. Here we summarize the most important findings: The distributor: It was found that the distributor in most of the rooms selected for field research, due to the small width of the structural model, is a width ranging between (90 to 110 cm) and its area varies between 2 m², as in a hotel room, and it reaches 2 6 m², as in a hotel room. See also the city chart showing the distributor area percentage out of the room's total area. Most dispensers have doors that open into the bathroom; no cabinets or storage areas can be arranged inside them. This sometimes prompted their arrangement within rooms and contributed to making the rooms more narrow and creating multiple functional and usability problems³.

The room: It became clear through field research regarding the architectural and interior distribution that there is diversity in the spatial dimensions of the rooms and the proportions of their deduction from the general area of the room. In general, most hotel rooms are narrow. This has hurt the functional distribution of interior furnishings and traffic in some models and has confused use, a lack of services, and deterioration of the spatial design and its environmental and physical conditions.

Chapter Three

Strategy for creating tourism excellence in hotels in Najaf Al-Ashraf

First: A detailed study of the internal and external standards of hotel projects

This element represents the clarification of the various fine details approved in the regulatory standards applied at the level of hotel projects, as we start from the external aspect to the most critical internal areas.

1- Definition of bioclimatic architecture: It stems from the nature of the region, from the determinants of location, orientation, and local building materials, not only artistically and aesthetically but also technically, with the determinants of heat, cold, and lighting. Therefore, architecture respects nature and its resources, providing its residents with the maximum possible environmental comfort. Bioclimatic architecture is a highly efficient organization compatible and harmonious with its local surroundings with minimal side effects. It always deals with the environment better and integrates with its determinants. Architecture stems from the nature of the region. It provides its residents with the maximum possible environmental comfort—relying as much as possible on natural energy without excessive consumption of traditional animation.

2- Principles of bioclimatic architecture: Energy efficiency and reliance on renewable natural energy sources fall under the following item:

- Compact thermal design to reduce the need to use air-handling devices.
- Providing the building with devices that convert natural energy into electricity and heat.
- The environmental dimension in the design process.
- The impact of construction on the natural environment.
- Economy in the use of resources, the most important of which is water.
- Achieving an indoor climate that works successfully and efficiently by considering insulation and controlling the internal air temperature, whether by cooling or heating.
- Respect the site's characteristics and reduce waste and misuse of building materials.

3- Objectives of bioclimatic architecture: The figure shows the objectives of bioclimatic architecture, and what can be achieved from its application is the integration of the building with its surroundings through the use of local materials and reliance on renewable natural energy sources to reduce excessive consumption of resources, to achieve an internal climate that works with high efficiency. It ensures the best level of comfort for users. This is what we tried to embody through the figure

Figure prepared by the researcher for the plan of goals of bioclimatic architecture, Figure (1)

- Basic strategies for bioclimatic design

Bioclimatic design attempts to reduce the use of effective systems in operating the building and rely on the local climate instead. The first step aims to know the autonomous systems that depend on the local climatic factors of the site and give priority to them instead of practical techniques. In this way, the design can achieve the most minor consumption of non-renewable energy. It is achieved through the morphological organization of the building's shape and its integration with

its surroundings. By using self-system strategies Through self-design through the use of wind and natural ventilation, self-design through solar control at the urban and building level, and self-design through facade design, as simple systems and techniques are used to reduce internal temperatures using natural energies by reducing the heat gained in the building and reducing entry into the building. Solar radiation passes through its outer shell, creating natural ventilation to achieve thermal comfort through special techniques. This can be achieved architecturally by the orientation of the building, its size, and location, the number of neighboring buildings, their location and formation, the external details of the building, the method of shading...etc.

Self-cooling systems are achieved by moving outside air and utilizing water, soil, and subsoil. Making the most of natural energies, as the formation is at the horizontal and vertical level of the building and the urban environment, and there are following forms that are optimal for each domain that help the designer to identify the mass and spatial formation of the neighborhoods and the urban fabric and its relationship with the ecological environment.

It is essential to protect the user from excessive heat in the summer. The principles of the heating strategy (passive solar heating systems) are capturing solar radiation, storing energy, collecting and distributing this heat in the building, regulating this heat, and finally avoiding losses and loss of power due to wind. This also applies in hot seasons, as heat consumption and cooling are undesirable. Necessary. This natural cooling strategy responds to summer luxury. It is about protecting the building from solar radiation and heat gain, reducing internal heat gain, dissipating heat, and cooling it naturally.

Second: The impact of interior design on the hotel capacity

Tourism activity in the holy city of Najaf depends mainly on the religious aspect, and this is due to the sacred shrines, shrines, and mosques that this city contains, which have a special place in the hearts of Muslims.

- 1- The number of hotels and their capacity: The Holy City of Najaf contained many religious monuments, so tourism activity began to move constantly, which contributed to establishing tourist hotels of various classification levels. The following table No. (1) shows the number of hotels and the number of rooms and beds for them in the City of Najaf. According to the classification degrees, the standards adopted by the Iraqi Tourism Authority Law No. (1) of 2004.

Table No. (1)

Source prepared by the researcher: The number of hotels in Najaf Al-Ashraf and their capacity

Number Of Beds	Number Of Suites	The Number Of Rooms	Number Of Hotels	Hotel Classification	N.
1080	13	444	4	First Degree	1
9073	8	3965	70	Second Degree	2
8615	3	2060	60	Third Degree	3
8249	Nothing	1086	48	Fourth Degree	4
27017	24	7555	182	The Total	

- 2- The Number of workers in the hotel sector in the Holy City of Najaf: The Number of workers in the hotel sector in the Holy City of Najaf is (2126, including permanent and temporary

foreigners and locals. This Number of workers is distributed according to the grades of hotels in the city, and the following table No. (2) shows the Number of employees in the hotel sector and according to the grades of these hotels.

Table No. (2)

The source was prepared by the researcher working in the hotel sector in the holy city of Najaf

The Total	Number Of Guards	Number Of Maintenance Workers	Number Of Employees	Hotel Classification	N .
149	4	10	135	First Degree	١
1100	70	140	890	Second Degree	٢
635	60	95	480	Third Degree	٣
242	48	50	144	Fourth Degree	٤
2126				Total number of employees	

3- A description of the production factors contributing to the hotel sector in the city of Najaf

A - The work element: The importance of this element in the hotel sector in the holy city of Najaf lies in many features that it demonstrates.

B - The capital component: The hotels in the holy city of Najaf do not rise to the level of first-class and excellent hotels and are mostly second-class, third-class, and fourth-class hotels. There is no superb-class hotel, and the first class is limited to only four hotels. The reason for this is the high cost of these hotels. Projects, so investors resorted to second- and third-class hotel projects due to the low price.

Most hotel projects in the holy city of Najaf are capital-intensive due to the high cost of buildings, construction, and furniture, in addition to the high land prices, as prices range between (5-30 million Iraqi dinars) per square meter depending on the distance and proximity to the religious site, and the value of the square meter One square meter of land purchased from the city municipality is worth 25% of the value of the prevailing price per square meter of land. These lands are small, as they were initially tiny houses before the city witnessed development on the hotel side to accommodate expatriates. The value of construction per square meter varies depending on the construction materials involved in the building and their quality, as well as the architectural designs and skilled hands working. Therefore, construction prices for hotel projects vary between (750,000 - 1,500,000) dinars per square meter, taking into account the high prices for building materials due to the Corona pandemic and also Due to the high cost of the dollar compared to the exchange rate of the local currency, as for hotel furnishing, the discrepancy is not large, but rather it is a relative discrepancy in the second and third levels due to the similarity of furnishing sources and quality in most hotels. According to recent estimates by furnishing contractors, it ranges

between (600 - 800) thousand dinars. Based on the above, the hotel project's capital will likely be intensive.

T - The element of attraction: Hotels in the Holy City of Najaf are distributed around or near the noble religious sites since these sites attract tourists and are distinguished by their population density. The Holy City of Najaf witnesses a distinguished presence of expatriates who are mainly classified within the religious tourism pattern, and this is reflected in the type of services offered by the city's hotels, which take a religious character. Based on this, the location of the hotel project has become a competitive advantage in terms of proximity or distance from the holy places, as hotels near the Haidari Mosque are distinguished in attracting several tourists. These hotels are close to The market because of the market's location close to the Haram. In addition to the distance and proximity to Haram and the market, there is an element of modernity, as it is considered an element of attraction in tourists' preference for one hotel over another. This element is closely related to the area of the hotel, as the areas of hotels close to the Haram are characterized by relatively small size compared to hotels far away. Especially those located between the cities of Najaf and Kufa. This smallness led to a relative decrease in occupancy efficiency compared to hotels far away, which will be explained later. This relative decrease is due to many religious tourist groups that cannot be included in a hotel close to Haram and the market.

D - Production characteristic: Hotel occupancy in the holy city of Najaf is trending in two directions: The first represents tourists arriving as individuals or families or local religious groups who reside in hotels that are not committed to accommodating them with tourism companies, and the second represents foreign religious groups whose tourism companies are bound by special contracts with private hotels to accommodate them throughout the year, in addition to the impact of the location factor that we mentioned previously, and based on that. Hotels' annual occupancy rates and annual revenues vary. Table No. (3) shows hotel occupancy rates, which range between (61% - 94%) and annual revenues, as well as the number of rooms offered and sold to hotels in the holy city of Najaf.

Table No. (3)

Source prepared by the researcher based on the figures of the Tourism Authority in Najaf Al-Ashraf: Hotel occupancy rate for hotels in Najaf Al-Ashraf

Annual revenue/in dollars	Number of rooms offered	Number of rooms sold	Hotel occupancy rate	Name of the tourist hotel	N.
802702	22320	19440	%87	Haidariya city	1
1289189	19440	16200	%83	Zamzam	2
173675	10440	8640	%82	Winner's paradise	3
218831	7200	6120	%85	The place	4
419594	23400	18000	%76	Ali Tower	5
486486	17280	13680	%79	Lion Palace	6
722972	21960	18000	%81	Al-Raqim	7
178783	8640	6480	%75	The heavy ones	8
353097	11160	7200	%64	The good	9

625232	24840	16560	%66	Bludan	10
467027	15480	13680	%88	Confirm	11
228000	11520	7920	%68	Papyrus	12
665756	17280	13320	%77	Durar Palace	13
1266385	33120	31320	%94	Granada	14
291891	17280	14400	%83	Arab Palace	15
1289189	42480	32400	%76	The land of the plain	16
425675	13680	11520	%84	Liwan	17
200000	9000	7200	%80	Giving City	18
788100	19440	16560	%85	The coupon	19
430540	11880	9000	% 75	Al-Ghalib's house	20

Conclusions

The research showed the role and importance of interior design for the tourist hotel room of the Holy City of Najaf. The responsibility lies primarily with the Tourism Authority in making the owners of these hotels commission specialized interior designers to provide interior designs with precisely defined specifications.

1- In addition to the direct results of the field and analytical study mentioned in the body of the research, it became clear that the design of residence rooms is characterized by the following:

2- Most research models' spatial and architectural dimensions (a room with two beds) do not conform to international controls and conditions. They are generally less or more significant than the global area (22.23 m²). The reason is that some of these hotels were converted from office buildings into hotels. It turned out that the licensing facilities were reflected in various problems (and a deterioration in the quality of functional, technical, and aesthetic interior design) not only in the hotel rooms but also in the rest of the hotel's functions.

3- The disappearance of the environmental and cultural dimension and the concept of sustainable design, particularly in the design of accommodation rooms. There are also no ecological components in terms of (the external environment) that appear in the hotel location, as all the hotels that are the subject of the study are concentrated in the commercial center, and this is not a defect in itself. Still, This retail center is located in the center of the city, and most of the city's transportation services are concentrated in it, which causes pollution resulting from congestion. This pollution includes visual chaos in the diversity of shapes, patterns, and colors, extreme poverty in the taste level, and auditory disorder resulting from the hustle and external noise in the streets and aesthetic deterioration. In the design and distribution of functions and exterior views.

4- There needs to be a unique identity and personal character for the hotel, which in turn is reflected in the design of the rooms, as all designs are similar externally and internally. There is no such thing as modern and contemporary interior design, and there is also no interior environmental design derived from cultural legacies. No local features are specific to the hotel and its rooms, making the structures lose the local spirit.

5- Some hotels have updated specific parts, such as bathrooms, using good elements and finishes with a practical and acceptable design in terms of appearance. The high occupancy rates of these

hotels hinder comprehensive methods. The Tourism Authority must implement timetables for repairs, maintenance, and complete design modification.

6- The presence of green interior elements and plant arrangements did not compensate for the absence of an external green environment. This demonstrates the designer's ignorance of the reality of the green environment and its role in giving the spontaneous and natural touch that the tourist needs

Recommendations

1- Enacting laws that specify the interior design conditions and specifications for a tourist hotel, taking into account the fulfillment of precisely defined requirements, first in terms of the quality and type of interior architectural design and the interior equipment for each category of hotel, including dimensions of spaces, quality of surfaces, testing of materials...etc., and second: about In the form, appearance, and style of interior design, the design is obligatory to refer to the cultural environment, achieve the goals of the concept of sustainable environmental design, keep pace with international standards, and pay attention to modern design trends.

2- Periodic interior design should be conducted to improve the design of accommodation rooms in terms of the level, quality, and style of their furnishings and furnishings.

3- This requires allocating a specialized interior designer to develop the designs. The designer must sign the contract, and a technical higher committee of engineers must be appointed to review and approve the plans and strategies.

4- The researcher believes that many factors contribute to the growth of the tourism industry, including propaganda and advertisement for tourism inside and outside Iraq.

5- Paying attention to activating and promoting tourism and hospitality through embassies, consulates abroad, and tourist offices

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